

Multifunctional hybrid metal oxide nanowire arrays for simultaneous green power generation and CO₂ reduction

Version 1

Description

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is developed in the Latvian Council of Science FLPP project No. lzp-2022/1-0239 "Multifunctional hybrid metal oxide nanowire arrays for simultaneous green power generation and CO₂ reduction" framework (project leader Dr. phys. Jana Andzane, 1st January 2023 - 31st December 2025, 300 000 EUR).

The Latvian national project is related to the development of innovative materials and methods for the development of green energy and the reduction of atmospheric CO₂. The materials developed in the project will serve as the basis for creating the new generation of multifunctional devices. By the end of the project, innovative nanostructured hybrid materials based on zinc and copper oxides will be developed, which will be used to create a device prototype for the simultaneous generation of electricity and reduction of CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere. The project will be implemented at the Institute of Chemical Physics of the University of Latvia in cooperation with the Institute of Solid State Physics (CFI) of the University of Latvia. The results of the project – innovative materials for simultaneous green energy generation and CO₂ reduction – will contribute to priorities 3 (Energy efficiency) and 6 (Knowledge base) of the smart specialization strategy for the transformation of the national economy, as well as contribute to the realization of the European green course.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

Fundamental and Applied
Research

Researchers

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Organizations

University of Latvia

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Multifunctional hybrid metal oxide nanowire arrays for simultaneous green power generation and CO2 reduction

Description:

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The Latvian national project is related to the development of innovative materials and methods for the development of green energy and the reduction of atmospheric CO2. The materials developed in the project will serve as the basis for creating the new generation of multifunctional devices. By the end of the project, innovative nanostructured hybrid materials based on zinc and copper oxides will be developed, which will be used to create a device prototype for the simultaneous generation of electricity and reduction of CO2 concentration in the atmosphere. The project will be implemented at the Institute of Chemical Physics of the University of Latvia in cooperation with the Institute of Solid State Physics (CFI) of the University of Latvia. The results of the project – innovative materials for simultaneous green energy generation and CO2 reduction – will contribute to priorities 3 (Energy efficiency) and 6 (Knowledge base) of the smart specialization strategy for the transformation of the national economy, as well as contribute to the realization of the European green course.

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Organizations:

University of Latvia

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#)

Grants: [Fundamental and Applied Research](#)

Project: [Multifunctional hybrid metal oxide nanowire arrays for simultaneous green power generation and CO2 reduction](#)

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date: [2025-03-18](#)

4. Templates

Descriptions

[WP1 Synthesis and structural characterization of hybrid nanowires](#)

This dataset includes the synthesis results of Cu-CuO-Cu₂O-ZnO hybrid nanowires and the investigation of their p-n junction for application in direct p-n junction thermoelectric generators. Hybrid nanowires will be synthesized by the combination of thermal oxidation and physical vapor deposition methods. Experimental characterization methods: scanning electron microscopy, X-ray diffraction, X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy, voltammetry.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

[1 Data Summary](#)

[1.1 Data Summary](#)

[1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected](#)

[Experimental data](#)

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- TIFF
- PNG
- XLS
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

1

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No similar data is available for Cu-CuO-Cu₂O-ZnO hybrid nanowires

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Target groups: world research society, research institutions for potential collaboration, manufacturing companies for potential further collaboration, general public (end-users).

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data will be available on reasonable request

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until publication

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Adobe Acrobat Reader, MS Office (Excel, Word, PowerPoint), Origin, Notepad, any image-viewing software

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-12-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2026-12-31

1 year after the end of the project

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Jana Andzane (0000-0002-9802-6895)

Overall project management and coordination, dissemination of the project results, organization of the day-to-day work, contact with controlling organizations, regular monthly round-table meetings of the project team, and organization of participation in public engagement events.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP2 Photovoltaic and thermal performance of hybrid nanowires under simulated solar illumination and external heat source

The dataset includes information about the properties of direct p-n junction CuO-Cu₂O-ZnO hybrid nanowires for application in direct p-n junction thermoelectric generators and photovoltaic cells.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The dataset includes the photovoltaic and thermal performance results of Cu-CuO-Cu₂O-ZnO hybrid nanowires in p-n configuration. The characterization of thermoelectric performance will include response to a heat source by measuring I-V curves, Seebeck coefficient, generated open circuit voltage per K, short circuit current density, testing of the hybrid nanowire arrays performance with different load resistances connected in series, determination of power conversion efficiency. The photovoltaic performance will include I-V curves measuring in the dark and under monochromatic light in UV-VIS-IR range, and under simulated solar illumination.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF

- CSV
- XLS
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

500

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No similar data is available for Cu-CuO-Cu₂O-ZnO hybrid nanowires

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Target groups: world research society, research institutions for potential collaboration, manufacturing companies for potential further collaboration, general public (end-users).

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data will be available on reasonable request

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until publication

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Adobe Acrobat Reader, MS Office (Excel, Word, PowerPoint), Origin, Notepad, any image-viewing software

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

No

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-12-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2026-12-31

1 year after the end of the project

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

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3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP3 CO2 reduction by hybrid nanowires under solar illumination/external heat

This dataset includes the results of testing the photocatalytic and thermocatalytic performance of the Cu-CuO-Cu₂O-ZnO hybrid nanowires in the continuous flow reactor. The photocatalytic and thermocatalytic reaction products will be determined using gas chromatography.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The dataset includes information about the photocatalytic and thermocatalytic performance of the Cu-CuO-Cu₂O-ZnO hybrid nanowires in the continuous flow reactor for CO₂ gas reduction. The mixture of CO₂ and H₂O vapour will be fed into the reactor, where the hybrid nanowires will be loaded. The catalytic activity will be activated by the illumination with the simulated solar light or by heating the sample. The reaction products will be determined using gas chromatography.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- PNG

- XLS

- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

600

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No similar data is available for Cu-CuO-Cu₂O-ZnO hybrid nanowires

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Target groups: world research society, research institutions for potential collaboration, manufacturing companies for potential further collaboration, general public (end-users).

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

Data will be available on reasonable request

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Until publication

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2.4 Increase data re-use

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2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2025-12-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2026-12-31

1 year after the end of the project

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

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Euro

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No

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No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

WP4 Proof-of-concept model for simultaneous energy generation under solar light/external heat and CO2 reduction

The dataset includes information about the proof-of-concept model/demonstrator of the device for simultaneous green power generation from solar light or external heat and CO2 reduction.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The dataset includes the methods for the fabrication of reliable high-quality durable electrical contacts to the Cu substrate and ZnO layer, wiring system, connectors to the measurement equipment, holder/case etc. for the proof-of-concept model/demonstrator of the device for simultaneous green power generation from solar illumination or external heat and CO2 reduction.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- ODT
- PNG
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

500

MB

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No

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